

PREVALENCE OF FACEBOOK ADDICTION, NARCISSISM AND SLEEP DISTURBANCES AMONG GRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study was intended to investigate the facebook addiction as a predictor of narcissism and sleep disturbances and also explore the relationship between these variables. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample of (N=630) graduate students from six different universities of Lahore in which (n=329) were male and (n=301) were female age range from 18 to 25 years. The (M=20.24) and (SD=1.63) was noted. The Bergen's Facebook Addiction Scale (Andreassen, 2012) was used to screen out the facebook addicts from non-addicts. The Narcissism Personality Inventory (Raskin and Hall, 1979) was used to access narcissism. The Pre-Sleep Arousal Scale (Shahzadi and Ijaz, 2014) was used to measure sleep patterns. The results indicated positive correlation between Facebook addiction, narcissism and sleep disturbances. It was observed that Facebook addiction positively predict sleep disturbances in students. Significant gender differences were also found in narcissism and sleep disturbances. It was found that males have more narcissistic personality trait as compared to females and females have more sleep disturbances as compared to males moreover higher prevalence of facebook addiction was found in females as compared to males. Results revealed that facebook addiction positively predict narcissism in students. The findings of the study may be beneficial for clinicians and parents to know the causes of sleep disturbances and narcissism in graduate students. Future researches may introduce some strategies and treatment plan for Facebook addiction, narcissism and sleep disturbances.

INTRODUCTION

The present research was conducted to investigate the prevalence of facebook addiction, narcissism and sleep disturbances among the graduate students. The people who have excessive usage of internet, i.e. facebook or other social networking sites, in their lives may have the narcissistic traits or sleep disturbances. The people use the facebook to communicate with friends, family and coworkers, peeping in to the lives of others, showing themselves to others, commenting on the events, playing games (Laurie & Paula, 2007).

Oberlin College of Computer Science (2016), proposed that because of being dependent on the Social Networking Sites, addicts can develop techno-stress where-in they only have ideas about how a computer works, such as accelerated time and perfect results. In the consequences it may cause social withdrawal, feeling more at comfort in communicating with people online rather than face to face.

According to Kimberly (2004) as the Internet entered in our lives at home, school, and work this study

proposed a workable definition of Internet addiction and as a newly introduced clinical phenomenon, highlights the consequences resulted by Internet addiction, including online affairs, student Internet abuse, and employee Internet abuse.

Since the topic of facebook addiction is relatively new and there has not been a definition developed or tested, it is first important to be sure that there is a common understanding between researchers of how facebook addiction is defined. Defining Facebook addiction should be done under the basis of using the facebook Intensity Scale developed by Ellison, Steinfield and Lampe (Laurie & Paula, 2007).

Addiction is the state of being enslaved to a habit or practice or to something that is psychologically or physically habit-forming, as narcotics, to such an extent that its cessation causes severe trauma. The term addiction has traditionally been used in relation to excessive and uncontrollable use of psychoactive chemicals such as alcohol and a wide variety of other drugs (Rachlin 1990; Walker 1989).

Addiction signifies repeatedly routines that aim to get chemicals and less frequently, routines without that goal. After some time is behavioral addictions, The urge to complete a behavior and discomfort if prevented from this resemble the craving and the withdrawal symptoms of substance abusers. Some withdrawal signs are common to many addictive syndromes while may be others are more specific (Mark 1990).

The facebook was introduced as an internet application (Zuckerberg, 2004). The ability to communicate with other people in real time, present oneself in the manner one desires, and develop a degree of intimacy may be addictive to some people, whereas simply gathering information and sending email may not be addictive (Martin & Schumacher, 2000; Scherer, Yang & Tung, 2007). It appears that specific applications are more addictive than others, namely those that are more interactive (Davis, 2001). The person who spent excessive time on the facebook and do not give time to the real world is said to be the facebook addict.

Facebook Addiction Disorder (FAD), is a condition that is defined by hours spent on facebook, in fact this is too much time that the health of the individual's life is affected. It is an estimate that around 350

million people were suffering from the disorder which was detected through a six-criterion sample set. People who were affected and aware of this condition must have at least 2-3 of the following criteria within 6-8 month time period (Amy, 2001).

There were many benefits of using facebook based upon free access, ease to dispatch as well as sharing personal information. Although, many issues like abuse, independency and addiction are likely to affect the life badly. The precedent study about use of electronic media like television, Internet, and Computer games have a link with sleep disorder as suggested by Van den Bulck Jin 2004 and Griffiths MD in 2012. Mechanism for this distinguish and include the use of many hours among dependent people changing their sleeping patterns, betting activities that are offered by facebook, among others. Sleep may have a remarkable left on mood and individual well-being, both the quantity and quality wise. Especially, in the case of teens, lack of sleep could have an adverse impact on educational performance as well (Gomes, 2011).

Drawbacks of facebook usage at first glance, facebook may seems like a positive gateway to connecting individuals and making it easier for people to stay in touch with those, to whom they had not connected with in the physical world in quite some time. The excessive use of this kind of social networks might cause several consequences including misuse, dependence and addiction, as well as potentially affecting life and sleep quality. Previous studies had shown that the use of electronic media, such as television, personal computers, internet, and computer games, was associated with sleep disorders. Mechanisms for this association were diverse and include the use of several hours among dependent people altering sleep patterns, the gambling activities that were provided by facebook platform, among others. However, young people were not even aware of the adverse effects of using electronic media. Both the quantity and the quality of sleep might had a strong influence on mood and subjective well-being. Especially, in the case of young people, a poor sleep quality could had an impact on academic performance as well (Wolniczak, et al., 2013).

Facebook had several advantages, based on the free access, facilitating communication as well as sharing

personal information. However, the excessive use of this kind of networks might cause several consequences including misuse, dependence and addiction, as well as potentially affecting life and sleep quality. Previous studies had been shown that the use of electronic media, such as television, personal computers, internet, and computer games, is associated with sleep disorders. Mechanisms for this association are diverse and include the use of several hours among dependent people altering sleep patterns, the gambling activities that were provided by the platform of facebook, among others. However, young people were not even aware of the adverse effects of using social media. Both the quantity and quality may had a strong effect on mood and subjective well-being. Especially, in case of young people a poor sleep quality could have an impact on academic performance as well (Wolniczak, et al., 2013).

Study conducted by Blachnio and Przepiorka (2016) show that facebook is getting popularity day by day and become one of the most common communication tool. With the increased number of face book users people were getting more addicted to that which disrupting the interpersonal relationships and give rise to phenomenon called facebook intrusion. The study showed whether unsubstantial self-control and self-regulation were the sources which cause the users for the facebook addiction. The finding showed that the users having insufficient self-control were having more facebook addiction. While the users who were self-disciplined and not focusing on negative emotions were able to resist the temptation of facebook addiction.

Study conducted by Amon, et al. (2016) revealed that health research can be done through facebook but literature regarding how facebook can be used to induct adolescents is lacking. For this purpose two types of posts were made to check the responses of fans on page. First type of posts was about events and study oriented posts. The second type of posts was related to current news, family and about adolescent posts. Observations to see the responses of users were made across one year through three phases (phase 1, very low facebook use; phase 2, high facebook use; phase 3, low facebook use). 88.6% of page fans were females with the age group between 35 to 44 years.

The findings showed the study oriented posts with photos were more liked by the fans.

A study concluded by Bessi, et al. (2016) that the users tends to gather and select the information that assist their beliefs and for the formation of eco chambers where they sharing the same views. For this purpose comparative study is conducted on how same contents such as videos were used on different social media like facebook and you tube. A sample of 12M users was considered. The findings of study showed that contents and users commenting patterns helps to form and show their formation of eco chambers on both social media platforms.

Study conducted by Cole-Lewis, et al. (2016) indicates that social media also helping the individuals to change their behavior such as quitting of smoking. By observing the association of participants in the groups of social media which were health related show that these groups tended to assist their behavior change

A research concluded by Dickson, et al., (2016) that facebook was getting popular now a days and its use also increased in rural areas. While getting so much popular facebook can be utilized to maintain contact with research participants and research can be done among areas which were hard to reach and at risk groups. The objective of this study was to utilize the facebook as the research follow up approach with drug using women in three rural jails in one state by conducting face to face interviews. The findings of research showed that among rural drug using women facebook was broadly used and accepted and it showed facebook can be used as research follow up approach for rural areas, hard to reach populations or geographically isolated regions.

Study conducted by Frison and Eggermont (2016) revealed that social media sites were ideal platform for negative comparison for the adolescent users who were experiencing negative feelings through social comparison. This negative comparison on social media had been related with user's well-being. The study was conducted among adolescents to examine this. The findings of cross lagged analysis showed that negative comparison cause decrease in life satisfaction over time. Lower life satisfaction showed increase in negative comparison on facebook.

Study conducted by Lee, et al. (2016) revealed that, the use of mobile texting and facebook had been

increased among every student and no research was done on the relationship of facebook usage and mobile texting and also their impact on the health of dental students. To study this factor a cross sectional study was conducted on Malaysia's private university students. Through questionnaire and interviews the study was conducted. Multiple regression analysis was applied to see the relationship between mobile texting and facebook use on health of students. The prevalence was 33.2% among more facebook users and 33% among more mobile texting. Facebook was found significantly related to the close friends, checking of updates on facebook of their friends and absence of feelings during facebook use. The findings showed the 33% students use the facebook and mobile texting excessively.

A study concluded by Moreno, et al. (2016) that the adolescents and adults were using and managing their social media "portfolio" on different sites like facebook and twitter but no research was done to see an individual behavior on displaying picture on these sites. The aim to that study was to check the behavior of students of college whether they display alcohol references on their sites of facebook and twitter. A large sample of students from two universities was gathered who are using both facebook and twitter. Data was collected by observing five months of participants their number of social connections and posts and posts of alcohol references. The findings showed that participants display alcohol references on facebook as compared on twitter. The result showed that participants have more social interaction and use on facebook as compared to twitter.

Study concluded by Morin, et al. (2016) that social media like facebook had changed the way of people interaction and socialization among people. This study was conducted to observe the facebook behavior in relation to psychological factors of stress. During adolescence the brain experience different important development and crucial class of stress hormones were known to harmonize its development. The psychosocial factors that may affect the emanation of stress hormones in adolescence. The research showed the relation between facebook behaviors and basal levels of cortisol between adolescent boys and girls. Perceived stress, perceived social support, self-esteem, and depressive symptoms were used as measures. The

findings showed that after controlling for sex, age, time of awakening, perceived stress, and perceived social support, cortisol had positive effect with number of facebook friends and negatively related with facebook peer interaction and no relation between depressive symptoms, self-esteem, and cortisol. The present study aims to explore the prevalence of Facebook addiction among students from six different universities in Lahore, while also examining its relationship with narcissistic personality traits and sleep disturbances. Additionally, the research investigates gender differences across all study variables and seeks to gather data on narcissistic behaviors among both teenage and adult university students. Lastly, the study assesses the impact of excessive Facebook usage on sleep disturbances within the student community.

Methodology

The design of present research project was a correlation research design. Correlational study is used to discover or establish the existence of a relationship between two or more aspects of a situation (Kumar, 2005). Correlation had been used as a method of the research to find a relationship between the variables, facebook use, narcissism, sleep disturbances and addictive tendencies. Participants were comprised of various graduate students from different universities of Lahore. Students with the age ranging from (18-25 years), ($M=20.24$, $SD=1.63$) were included in the study. The sample ($N=630$) was comprised of males ($n=329$) and females ($n=301$). All participants were selected from six different universities of city Lahore. Purposive sampling technique was used. Students who were spending at least three or more hours on social media were selected. Graduate students above 25 years and below 18 years were not selected for current research.

Demographic Information

The questionnaire comprised a series of basic demographic questions (e.g., age, gender, occupation, location) as well as some measures of facebook addiction, self-esteem, and life satisfaction. Two methods were used connected with extensive facebook usage, the first one measuring only the intensity of use, and the second one measuring not

only the intensity but also the consequences of this use. The methods used in the study have been widely applied in the subject literature, have good theoretical background, and showed good reliability in previous studies.

Demographic information also included the items like education, facebook usage as the students were asked, do you have facebook account? How many hours you use facebook per day? Sleep pattern was measured by asking the students, how many hours do you sleep per day? In the same way self-image was measured by asking, do you look at mirror for a long time in a day? Do you use facebook to share selfies with friends on facebook?

Bergen's Facebook Addiction Scale (2012)

For measuring facebook addiction, used the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS) (Andreassen et al., 2012). The scale has 18 items, 3 items per each symptom of addiction, the symptoms being: salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse (Andreassen et al., 2012). Permission was acquired from Andreassen, the developer of scale. The last version of the measure has 6 items, one per each symptom. Chose the items with loadings ranged from 0.80 to 0.84. The Cronbach's a reliability of the scale was 0.92. The range of the Facebook Addiction Scale was from 1 to 5. A higher score indicates a more severe level of facebook addiction. Bergen's Facebook Addiction Scale is a scale to assess the facebook addiction. The scale is based on work of Andreassen, 2012. It consists of six items related to facebook usage behaviors. All items are scored on the following scale: 1: Very rarely, 2: Rarely, 3: Sometimes, 4: Often, 5: Very often. The 3-week test-retest reliability will be high ($r > .75$). The scoring of the scale is as higher the scores indicate high level of addiction. The Bergen's Facebook Addiction Scale can be applied on every age group.

Narcissism Personality Inventory (1979)

The narcissism personality inventory was developed by Raskin and Hall (1979) for the measurement of narcissism. The test consists of forty pairs of statements, and it takes five to ten minutes to complete. It is important to consider which traits are dominant for example an over-all score that reflects

more points on vanity entitlement exhibitionism and exploitativeness is more cause for concern than someone who scores high on authority self-sufficiency and superiority so he presents seven component traits in scale. The sub-scales of the Narcissism Personality Inventory were Authority, Self-sufficiency, Superiority, Exhibitionism, Exploitativeness, Vanity and Entitlement.

Pre-sleep Arousal Scale (2014)

The pre-sleep arousal scale was developed by Shahzadi and Ijaz in 2014. The scale was developed to measure sleep problems in university students. It was 10 item scale measures somatic and cognitive arousal problems in students. Cronbach alpha of the test was 0.89 and test retest reliability was 0.87. The scale measures two factors. 8 items of the scale measure Somatic Arousal and the remaining 8 items measure Cognitive Arousal.

Procedure

After discussion with supervisor, the topic of the research was selected. The relevant and reliable tools were searched for data collection. Afterwards the authors of the tools were emailed for permission of tools usage. The author granted permissions to use and translate the tools. Three professors from university were selected for translation procedure. First professor translated English version into Urdu which was translated to English by second professor while the third professor converted the English translation into Urdu. Real and translated tools were discussed with supervisor and selected ones were used for data collection. After getting the permission to use the tools an official letter for data collection was obtained from the chairperson of the department of psychology university of Sargodha Lahore campus. The letter was signed by concerned persons of selected universities in order to grant the permission of data collection from university students. The willing participants were selected according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample of whole population. All participants were informed about the nature of research and assured that confidentiality must be considered. Participants were requested to read carefully and sign consent form initially. Participants

were requested to fill the demographic form. The 630 participants were selected from different universities and given three questionnaires named as Bergen’s Facebook Addiction Scale, Narcissistic Inventory and Pre-sleep Arousal Scale respectively to answer. The total time consumed for the answering of tools was calculated as 20 minutes. Approximately three months were consumed in order to collect data. The collected data was put into the SPSS and results were generated.

Ethical Considerations

All research procedure was completed under ethical consideration. Informed consents were taken from the participants. Confidentiality of their identity and information was made sure. Risk/benefit ratio was measured and the benefits of the study were higher than the risks. Formal permission to carry out the research project was taken from the chairperson of the department of psychology university of Sargodha Lahore campus and an official letter was obtained from the supervisor for data collection.

Analytical Techniques

The data collected was analyzed using SPSS software in order to gather statistical evidences of the variables tested. The confidence interval for performance determined the sampling errors. Further, the mean and standard deviation was measured for each

response using descriptive statistics. For each mean declared, the confidence interval was established. Linear regression was conducted to test significance for variables, Facebook usage and factors that are predicted to influence it. Correlations were conducted to further test whether there was a relationship between two variables and to test hypothesis predicted.

Results

The current study aimed to investigate the relationship between facebook addiction, narcissism, and sleep disturbances among graduate students. The data analytical strategy involved,

- a) Descriptive analysis to find out the descriptive statistics of study variables
- b) Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was used to assess the relationship between narcissism, sleep disturbances and Face book addiction among graduate students.
- c) Regression analysis was carried out to find the predictors of narcissism and sleep disturbances in students.
- d) Independent samples t-test analysis was used to find out gender differences in narcissism, sleep disturbances and Facebook addiction among young adults.

Demographic Characteristics of the sample are given below (see table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N=630)

Characteristics	f	%	M	SD
Age(years)			20.24	1.63
Education				
1st year	235	37.30		
2nd year	151	24.00		
3 rd year	121	19.20		
4th year	123	19.50		
Family System				
Joint	265	42.10		
Separate	365	57.90		
Birth order				
1-3	497	78.90		
4-6	114	18.09		
7-9	19	3.01		
No. of Siblings				
1-4	387	61.40		

5-9	238	37.77
10-13	5	0.79

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Reliability Analysis of the Study Variables

Variables	N	M	SD	α	Range		Skewness
					Potential	Actual	
Facebook Addiction Scale	630	13.37	4.34	.65	6-30	6-30	0.400
Narcissism Scale total	630	61.31	4.00	.63	40-80	40-78	-0.102
Authority	630	12.38	1.43	.59	8-16	8-16	-0.041
Self Sufficiency	630	9.37	1.25	.60	6-12	6-12	-0.153
Superiority	630	7.62	1.28	.62	4-10	4-10	-0.120
Exhibitionism	630	10.96	1.13	.69	7-14	7-14	-0.094
Exploitativeness	630	7.89	1.07	.67	5-10	5-10	-0.254
Vanity	630	4.14	0.75	.55	3-6	3-6	0.268
Entitlement	630	8.96	1.26	.68	6-12	6-12	-0.102
Sleep total	630	38.65	10.62	.84	16-80	16-68	0.103
Somatic problems	630	15.99	5.89	.77	8-40	8-38	0.672
Cognitive Problems	630	14.18	4.61	.76	5-25	5-25	-0.005
Sleep Problems	630	8.48	2.52	.35	3-15	3-15	-0.160

Table 2 shows the reliability of the scales. Facebook Addiction Scale has 0.65 Cronbach’s Alpha value which depicts that it is reliable scale for measuring facebook addiction. Similarly, Narcissism scale has 0.63 Cronbach’s Alpha value and its subscales have Cronbach’s Alpha values ranges from 0.55 to 0.69. Alpha reliability coefficients show that narcissism is reliable scale to measure personality of the subjects. Sleep scale also have high Cronbach’s Alpha value. The range of its subscales is 0.35 to 0.77. The lowest value was 0.35 for sleep problem subscale. Univariate analysis confirmed that all the scores were normally distributed i.e., value of skewness was less than 2.

Table 3: Overall Prevalence of Facebook Addiction among Students (N=630)

Variables	N= 630	Male (n=329)	Female (n=301)
Facebook Addiction	25.07%	22.79%	25.57%

Table 3 shows the overall prevalence of the facebook addiction among university students. The prevalence of facebook addiction among students of six most renowned universities of Lahore was 25.07% whereas higher prevalence was noted in females as compared to males.

Table 4: Correlations between Narcissism, Sleep Disturbances and Facebook Addiction in Students.

Scale	Sub-scale	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	M	SD
Narcissism	1.Authority	-	.28*	.26*	.12*	.19*	.21*	.21*	.63*	-	-.05	-.05	.01	3.8	1.5
			**	**	*	**	**	**	**	.0				7	1
Personality	2.Self sufficiency	-	.20*	.14*	.14*	.11*	.18*	.55*	-	-	-	-.01	2.5	1.2	
			**	**	**	*	**	**	.1	.15*	.15*		5	5	
Inventory	3.Superiority	-	.17*	.15*	.26*	.18*	.59*	-	-.05	-.04	-.01	2.3	1.3		
			**	**	**	**	**	.0				5	0		
	4.Exhibitions	-	.14*	.32*	.19*	.55*	.0	.04	.07	.16*	2.3	1.3			
			**	**	**	**	.0	.04	.07	**	1	6			
	5.exploitativeness	-	.11*	.07	.45*	-	.07	-.06	.11*	1.6	1.1				
			*		**	.0		*	0	0					
	6.vanity	-	.13*	.50*	.0	-.05	-.04	.08*	1.1	.87					
			*	**	.0				4						
	7.Entitlement	-	.53*	-	.07*	.02	.02	2.7	1.2						
			**	.0				6	9						
	8.Narcissism total	-	-.06	-.06	.09*	16.	4.7								
			.0			61									
Per-sleep Arousal Scale	9.Somatic problems	-	.52*	.86*	.19*	16.	5.8								
			**	**	**	01	8								
	10.Cognitive problems	-	.88*	.23*	22.	6.2									
			**	**	69	7									
Bergen's Facebook Addiction Scale	11.Sleep problems	-	.24*	38.	10.										
			**	71	60										
	12.Facebook Addiction	-	13.	4.3											
			36	4											

*p <.05, **p <.01, ***p <.001

Results in table 4 indicated that authority has significant positive relationship with narcissism and its components (self-sufficiency, superiority, exhibitionism, exploitativeness, vanity, and entitlement). Self sufficiency has significant positive relationship with superiority, exhibitionism, exploitativeness, vanity, and entitlement while it has negative relationship with sleep disturbances in graduate students. Superiority is significantly positively related with exhibitionism, exploitativeness, vanity, and entitlement. Exhibitionism personality

trait has significant positive relationship with exploitativeness, vanity, entitlement and facebook addiction. Exploitativeness is significantly positively related with vanity and facebook addiction in students. Vanity personality trait and sleep disturbances are positively related with facebook addiction.

It was hypothesized that facebook addiction is likely to be the predictor of narcissism in students. For this purpose, a series of regression analysis was performed by using enter method.

Table 5: Facebook Addiction as a Predictor of Narcissism among Students.

Predictors	Narcissism											
	Narcissism			Authority			Self Sufficiency			Superiority		
	B	SE	β	B	SE	β	B	SE	β	B	SE	β
Constant	18.42	2.76		3.87	.87		3.47	.72		4.14	.75	
Facebook Addiction	.09	.04	.08*	-.01	.01	-.01	-.02	.01	-.01	-.01	.01	-.01
Age	-.06	.12	-.02	.01	.04	.02	-.01	.03	-.01	-.06	.03	-.08*
Gender	-.75	.39	-.07	-.23	.12	-.07	-.24	.10	-.09*	-.13	.12	-.05
Family system	-.56	.39	-.06	.05	.12	.01	-.22	.10	-.08*	-.14	.12	-.05
R ²	.02			.01			.02			.01		
F	2.94*			1.02			2.86*			1.67		

*p <.05, **p <.01, ***p <.001

Table 5 continued: Facebook Addiction as a Predictor of Narcissism among Students

Predictors	Narcissism											
	Exhibitionism			Exploitativeness			Vanity			Entitlement		
	B	SE	β	B	SE	β	B	SE	β	B	SE	β
Constant	2.56	.78		.34	.64		.92	.50		3.40	.75	
Facebook Addiction	.05	.01	.16***	.03	.01	.11**	.02	.01	.08*	.01	.01	.01
Age	-.03	.03	-.04	.04	.03	.06	-.01	.02	-.01	-.02	.03	-.02*
Gender	.01	.11	.01	-.06	.09	-.03	.04	.07	.02*	-.13	.10	-.05
Family system	-.18	.11	-.07	.04	.09	.01	-.04	.07	-.02*	-.04	.10	-.02
R ²	.03			.02			.01			.01		
F	4.89**			2.79*			1.34*			.54		

*p <.05, **p <.01, ***p <.001

Results in table 5 revealed that facebook addiction positively predicted narcissistic personality traits in students. The explained variance for the overall model was 2%. Gender negatively predicted self sufficiency personality trait which indicate that males have higher self sufficiency as compare to females. Family system negatively predicted self sufficiency which means that

students in joint family system have more self sufficiency personality traits as compare to students in separate family system. The explained variance for the overall model was 2%. It was revealed that facebook addiction predicted exhibitionism, exploitativeness, and vanity personality traits. Gender positively predicted vanity, it indicated that females are higher

on vanity personality traits as compare to males. Family system negatively predicted vanity which indicates that students in separate family system have more vanity personality traits as compare to joint family system. The overall explained variance for

Exhibitionism was $R^2= 3\%$, for Exploitativeness $R^2= 2\%$, for vanity and entitlement $R^2 =1\%$.

It was hypothesized that facebook addiction is likely to be the predictor of sleep disturbances in students. For this purpose, a series of regression analysis was performed by using enter method (see table 6).

Table 6: Facebook Addiction as a Predictor of Sleep Disturbances in Students

Predictors	Sleep Disturbances			Somatic Arousal			Cognitive Arousal		
	B	SE	β	B	SE	β	B	SE	B
Constant	25.23	5.93		7.44	3.32		17.67	3.52	
Facebook Addiction	.59	.09	.24***	.26	.05	.19***	.33	.06	.23***
Age	.10	.25	.01	.16	.14	.04***	-.06	.15	-.01
Gender	2.40	.83	.11**	1.71	.47	.14***	.70	.49	.05*
Family system	-.06	.84	.01	-.45	.47	-.04	.42	.50	.03
R^2	.07			.06			.06		
F	11.97***			9.54***			9.81***		

*p <.05, **p< .01, ***p < .001

Results revealed that facebook addiction positively predicted sleep disturbances overall and its components (Somatic Arousal and Cognitive arousal) in students. Age positively predicted Somatic arousal. Gender positively predicted sleep disturbances, it indicated that females experience more sleep problems as compare to males.

It was hypothesized that significant difference is likely to be found between male and female Face book addicts regarding narcissism and sleep disturbances. In order to examine gender differences in narcissistic personality traits, sleep disturbances and facebook addiction in students, independent sample t-test was carried out (see table 7).

Table 7: Results of t-test and Descriptive Statistics for Facebook Addiction, Narcissism, and Personality in Male and Female Students(N=630)

Variables	Male			Female			t-value
	M	SD	n	M	SD	n	
Facebook Addiction	13.36	4.25	329	13.37	4.41	301	-0.04
Narcissism total	16.99	4.97	329	16.19	4.57	301	2.09*
Authority	3.99	1.53	329	3.75	1.48	301	1.93
Self sufficiency	2.68	1.25	329	2.42	1.24	301	2.63*
Superiority	2.40	1.31	329	2.29	1.30	301	1.10
Exhibitionism	2.31	1.36	329	2.31	1.37	301	0.01
Exploitativeness	1.64	1.07	329	1.56	1.14	301	0.93
Vanity	1.12	0.88	329	1.16	0.85	301	-0.58
Entitlement	2.82	1.32	329	2.70	1.27	301	1.17

Sleep total	37.49	9.91	329	39.93	11.21	301	-2.88**
Somatic problems	15.26	5.30	329	16.83	6.37	301	-3.35 **
Cognitive problems	13.90	4.38	329	14.48	4.84	301	-1.59
Sleep problems	8.37	2.55	329	8.61	2.49	301	-0.119

*Significant at 0.05 level of significance,

**Significant at 0.01 level of significance

The result revealed that significant gender differences are found in narcissism personality traits and sleep disturbances. It is found that male have more narcissistic personality traits overall ($M=16.99$, $SD=4.97$) as compare to female ($M=16.19$, $SD=4.57$), $t(628) = 2.09$, $p = .03$. Male are higher on self sufficiency personality traits ($M= 2.68$, $SD= 1.25$) than female ($M= 2.42$, $SD= 1.24$), $t(628) = 2.63$, $p= .01$. Female experience more sleep problems ($M= 39.92$, $SD= 11.23$) as compare to male ($M= 37.59$, $SD= 9.87$), $t(628) = -2.76$, $p= .01$. Female also experience more somatic problems related to sleep ($M= 16.83$, $SD= 6.37$) as compare to male ($M= 15.26$, $SD= 5.30$), $t(628) = -3.35$, $p= .001$.

Summary of the Finding

1. Self-sufficiency personality trait has significant negative relationship with sleep disturbances while exhibitionism personality trait has significant positive relationship with Facebook addiction in students.
2. Exploitativeness is significantly positively related with Facebook addiction and Facebook addiction has significant positive relationship with vanity personality trait and sleep disturbances in students.
3. Results also revealed that Facebook addiction positively predicted narcissistic personality traits (exhibitionism, exploitativeness, and vanity) personality traits in students.
4. Results showed that Facebook addiction positively predicted sleep disturbances overall and its components (Somatic Arousal and Cognitive arousal) in students.
5. The result revealed that significant gender differences were found in narcissism personality traits and sleep disturbances. It was

found that males have more narcissistic personality traits as compare to females while female experience more sleep problems as compare to male.

6. The prevalence of facebook addiction was significantly higher in females than males.

Discussions

The present study was aimed to predict the facebook as future threat to narcissism and sleep disturbances among graduate students. For this purpose, the scales of Bergen's Facebook Addiction scale, Narcissism Personality Inventory and Pre-Sleep Arousal scale were used.

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between narcissism and facebook addiction as most of the users were found involved in picture and movie sharing of different events, sharing their status of activities and involved in finding appraisals from friend list.

Facebook addiction was a common problem among young generation. The facebook usage had been observed more common during class timings, traveling hours, sleeping time, social gathering and meeting hours. It was observed that youngsters under 25 had strong addiction tendency to facebook than older people (Chao Lin., et al., 2012). As the present study shown that overall prevalence of facebook addiction is 25.07% and age range is under 25.

Facebook addiction caused problems in social relations and daily life. According to Harzadin (2012) facebook addicts had problem with their families, friends, jobs and school environments. Addicts start spending less time with their friends, relatives and families. Moreover they start to remain at home almost all day. They could be passive to the events that

occur in their environment when they were in front of facebook screen.

Jha, et al., (2016) conducted a study to explore facebook effects on various dimensions of Nepalese student population. Results of the study closely resemble to results obtained in current study, 4.2 % of the students admitted accessing facebook during the classroom lectures. Whereas in present study it was 25.07% student fall is facebook addiction.

A cross-sectional study was conducted to determine the prevalence of facebook addiction among students. The Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS) was used. The results of this study showed that the overall prevalence of facebook addiction amongst students was 41.8% and a high rate was noted in females than males (MM MPH, 2015). This study also supported the results of present study as results shown higher prevalence in females which is 25.57% than males which is 22.79%

Jha, at el. (2016) study is also closely related to the present study, indicated that one-fourth of the students acknowledged that they were using facebook late at night on a regular basis. Almost two-third of the users further admitted that facebook has had a negative impact on their studies. Burning eyes (21 %), disturbed sleep (19 %), and headache (16 %) were the most common adverse health effects reported by the facebook users. In the present study results also revealed that facebook addiction positively predicted sleep disturbances overall and its components (Somatic Arousal and Cognitive arousal) in students. Age positively predicted Somatic arousal. Gender positively predicted sleep disturbances, it indicated that women experience more sleep problems as compare to men. The result showed that significant gender differences are found in narcissism personality traits and sleep disturbances.

Davis (2001) has told about the distal and proximal factors associated with the use of Internet. According to Davis, distal factors associated with the Internet use refer to the underlying psychopathology.

The relationship between Internet addiction and self-esteem has been discussed in several studies. In these studies, personality traits, self-esteem and other psychiatric disorders were shown to be associated with Internet addiction (Griffiths, 2000; 2008). In the present study several components of personality traits

has shown significant positive relation with facebook addiction. The results show that self-sufficiency has significant positive relationship with superiority, exhibitionism, exploitativeness, vanity, and entitlement while it has negative relationship with sleep disturbances in graduate students.

Superiority is significantly positively related with exhibitionism, exploitativeness, vanity, and entitlement. Exhibitionism personality trait has significant positive relationship with exploitativeness, vanity, and entitlement and facebook addiction.

Exploitativeness is significantly positively related with vanity and facebook addiction in students. Vanity personality trait and sleep disturbances are positively related with facebook addiction. Results revealed that facebook addiction positively predicted narcissistic personality traits in students.

A recently published American Academy of Pediatrics (2010) paper made a major splash when it described facebook depression: a condition said to result when teens spend too much time on social media, leading them to turn to “substance abuse, unsafe sexual practices, or aggressive or self-destructive behaviors.

Limitations and Suggestions

Some limitations had been noted in the present research and suggestions in the light of these limitations are given for further researches regarding the betterment of research work.

1. In the present study data was collected form the participants of Lahore City, this study can be extended on the whole population of Pakistan to assess the causes of prevalence of facebook addiction, narcissism and sleep disturbances.
2. In present study the population was not easily agreed to provide detailed information about their routine and personal life.
3. Exams session was on, so the students were not easily approachable.

Implications and Recommendations

1. The present research was conducted to study the relationships between facebook addiction, narcissism and sleep disturbances. Theoretical evidences suggested that in Pakistan major focus of researchers was on chemical addiction rather than behavioral addictions. The present study was an attempt to bring forth the effects of facebook

addiction as it was emerging cause of disturbed personalities and sleep patterns.

2. Nowadays, people started suffering to become addicts to computers, mobile phones and finally social networking sites. This survey possessing a descriptive design was implemented on the students of different educational institutes from different faculties and colleges. According to results of the study, 5.1% of the students, joining the survey were addicts and 22.6% of them were in the risky groups.
3. When these results were taken into account, it was clearly said that 25.07% of participants were Problematic and facebook addict. When it was compared with other categories, user who use facebook everyday regularly and use computer and mobile phone to connect facebook were more susceptible to face book addiction. The survey also showed a positive and meaningful relation between daily face book usage time of participants and loneliness level of participants with addiction level. In other words, when participants' facebook usage time and their feeling of loneness in social life increase, their facebook addiction level also increases at the same time. That was why, it could be clearly said that there was a direct proportional relation these two different variables. In reality, spending too much time on face book causes users to stay at home so long and also it cause users to spend little time with their friends or relatives in social life. Because of this, these kinds of users that are addicts become too passive to events and social life realizing their environment.

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